

Annotation

In this article, the improvement of these technologies in terms of the structural content of various concentration training models has been thought about. Also, a one-time study of a topic, section or entire academic discipline, ensuring their solid assimilation; direction of the educational process towards the development of creative activity of students; creating favorable conditions for cooperation between teachers and students, successful integration of theory and practice, and the formation of unique knowledge and skills in students; it is clearly shown that it is necessary to use a set of forms of educational organization that adequately implements the holistic process of cognition

Key words: concentration, attention, types of attention, Intensity, pedagogical terminology, creative activity, scientific research, educational day, class-lesson system

Аннотация

В этой статье совершенствование этих технологий с точки зрения структурного содержания различных моделей тренировки концентрации думало. Также единоразовое изучение темы, раздела или всей учебной дисциплины с обеспечением их прочного усвоения; направление образовательного процесса на развитие творческой активности студентов; создание благоприятных условий для сотрудничества преподавателей и студентов, успешной интеграции теории и практики, формирования у студентов уникальных знаний и умений; наглядно показано, что необходимо использовать совокупность форм образовательной организации, адекватно реализующую целостный процесс познания.

Ключевые слова: концентрация, внимание, виды внимания, интенсивность, педагогическая терминология, творческая деятельность, научные исследования, учебный день, классно-урочная система.

Concentration - Latin "con" (cum) - together and "centrum" — Center-the accumulation of something in a certain place.

The word "concentration" (concentration) basically means two:

1. Physics or chemistry: the amount of a substance within a certain amount of volume or mass. For example, the concentration of salt in the solution.
2. Mental focus: concentration of attention in one place, focusing all attention on one task or activity. For example, it is important to have a high concentration in learning a lesson.

Attention is the involvement of a subject's activity in an object or phenomenon. It is a necessary condition for the effectiveness of any conscious activity. Sources of optimal arousal in certain areas of the cerebral cortex form the physiological basis of attention.

Attention is divided into two types:

1. Involuntary (passive) attention. Involuntary attention is generated regardless of the desire of a person under the influence of some external cause. Such attention does not require willpower from a person. The power of the trigger is of great importance to attract attention; for example, the beauty, brightness, sharp smell and other properties of a thing involuntarily attract attention.

2. Optional (active) attention. In voluntary attention, psychic activity is consciously attracted to a certain thing with a predetermined goal. This type of focus requires willpower; therefore, this focus is also known as volitional focus. The entire conscious activity of a person is carried out mainly through the means of voluntary attention.

Attention plays a key role in the process of receiving and processing this information. This involves filtering information using directed attention and excluding information that is not needed.

Concentration, on the other hand, is the process of directing and maintaining a long-term focus on a task or activity. This involves focusing attention on a specific goal and avoiding distractions. Concentration requires achieving and maintaining long-term attraction.

Concentration and attention are processes in close contact with each other. While attention is focused on receiving and processing more information, concentration requires effective management of these processes in the long run. Concentration and attention are important in a person's efficiency, educational process and life. Although they are in close contact with each other, they have their own characteristics. Let's give a broader overview of their commonalities, differences and which one should be given priority.

Commonalities

Attention and focus: both concepts are important in the perception and processing of information. They involve human processes of receiving information, directing attention to a point, and filtering information.

Learning process: concentration and Focus are both important in the learning process. Attention is needed to quickly and efficiently receive information, and concentration is necessary to carry out long-term tasks. For example, in a mathematics lesson, attention is important because it ensures the acceptance of new information, but concentration helps in solving long-term issues.

Differences

Duration: attention is often short-lived, requiring attention to a specific task. Concentration, on the other hand, is long-term and requires long-term attention retention to complete a given task. .

Intensity: attention can change quickly and focus on multiple tasks at the same time. Concentration, on the other hand, requires a fully focused focus on one task.

Ingredients: attention is a component of concentration. With the help of attention, it is possible to perform long-term tasks by receiving information and then concentrating.

Which one should be given priority?

Which one should be given priority in the educational process depends on a particular case, both equally important. Because they complement each other. Attention helps to receive information quickly and efficiently, while concentration is important in long-term storage and application of that information. The effectiveness of attention comes from concentration, and vice versa. However, in long-term tasks, concentration should be prioritized, as this ensures

complete completion of the task. Also concentration interprets the primacy in the following types:

Stability: concentration requires long-term and stable attention. For example, a researcher can work for several hours or even days to solve a problem, focusing their attention on that problem.

Persistence: in the process of concentration, a person must fully focus on a task, without spreading his attention. For example, the photographer Mukhim needs to fully concentrate on his camera in order to capture a moment.

Attention, on the other hand, is in the following aspects:

Mobility: attention can change rapidly, which means that a person can focus on several things at the same time. For example, a teacher can answer several students' questions at the same time during the course of a lesson.

Breadth: attention can be broad, meaning that students can focus on several things at the same time. This helps them to receive and process different information at the same time in the learning process. For example, in the course of a written work, the reader can both read the information and write down his thoughts.

If we focus on the above - mentioned tariff of concentration concentration-mental attention. This represents the active type of attention.

Research carried out in Kazan in the late 19th century by employees of the RAO SSO Research Institute finally introduced the concept of "concentrated education" into the pedagogical lexicon.

In pedagogical terminology, the concept of "concentrated education" has long been firmly established. It cannot be said that it is used everywhere in the literature on didactics, but it would also be wrong to say that it is not included in the pedagogical thesis. For example, in the 1920s and 30s, it began to be widely used in the description of the method of cyclic teaching in Soviet didactics: "the cyclic system is sometimes called a concentrated teaching system, since the teaching material is concentrated at small intervals". The concept of "concentration" firmly entered the lexicon of scientists engaged in various studies in the 1970s.

The organization of teaching in such a system was considered by many authors and named differently by them. For Example, G.A.Kitaygorodskaya uses the term "intensive preparation". V.G.Anushkin, Yu.N.Kulyutkin, G.D.Glazer on the "education of stsic"; M.P. Shchetinin, G.V.Serkutyev, V.S.Bezrukova-about the "bathing method"; L.Efremenko, G.I.Ibragimov uses the term "concentrated training". Linguistic analysis A.A.The term "concentrated learning", implemented by Ostapenko, in the opinion of many, fully reveals the essence of this pedagogical phenomenon: "combining each topic into blocks, reducing the number of days, aimed at a deeper study of the attention of teachers and students, are disciplines studied in parallel during the week." Conditions and various aspects of this pedagogical Technology M.P.Shchetinin, V.S.Bezrukova, G.I.Ibragimov, N.N.Nozaдзе, G.V.Serkutyeva, N.M.Talanchuk et al.A.Ostapenko was considered in 2014.

While the concepts of "concentrated education" and "concentrated teaching" are related, they have different meanings:

1. Concentrated education:

- This method of education implies intensive study of educational materials in a short time. Students gain in-depth knowledge of a particular subject or field over a period of time.

- For example, Summer Intensive Courses, short-term trainings or special programs.

2. Concentration training:

- This teaching method is carried out by the teacher by focusing the attention and attention of the students in one place. This technique is used for students to better understand and assimilate the material.

- For example, through activities that attract attention, interactive methods or specific strategies.

Thus, concentrated education refers to a short-term, intensive educational process, while concentrated teaching is the sum of methods that ensure the concentration of students ' attention and its effective management.

References:

- 1.Ибрагимов Г.И. Технология концентрированного обучения. Метод, рекомендации. - Наб. Челны: Камаз, 1992. - 32с
- 2.Остапенко А.А. Концентрированное обучение: модели образовательной технологии.- Шк. техн. - 1999.- S.- С.116-154.
- 3.ОстапенкоА.А.Онтогенез и интедиффия непрерывного образования.- Шк. техн. - 2000,- 1.- С.73-78.
- 4.Безрукова.В.С. Концентрированное обучение педагогике («погружение»)// Интеграционные процессы в педагогической теории и практике : сб. научн. трудов - Свердловск: СИПИ. - 1991. - с. 102-113
(<https://thisvsthat.io/attention-vs-concentration>)

